

MEAN CHANGE IN INTRAOCULAR PRESSURE (IOP) AFTER INTRAVITREAL AVASTIN IN NON-GLAUCOMATOUS PATIENTS WITH MACULAR EDEMA

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Abstract

Objective: To calculate the mean change in the intraocular pressure (IOP) after intravitreal avastin in non-glaucomatous patients with macular edema presenting in patients coming to tertiary care Hospital Karachi.

Methods: This quasi-experimental study was conducted at the Department of Ophthalmology, Liaquat National Hospital Karachi, from November 11th 2024 to April 12th 2025, using non-probability consecutive sampling. Individuals aged 30 to 55 years with non-glaucomatous macular edema were included, while patients treated with platelet-rich plasma, those with a history of trauma, or using beta blockers or steroid-containing eye drops were excluded to avoid confounding and bias. All eligible patients underwent comprehensive ophthalmic and systemic examinations, including unaided and best-corrected visual acuity using Snellen charts, slit lamp examination, fundus examination, intraocular pressure measurement via contact tonometry. A detailed medical history was recorded. Intravitreal injections of bevacizumab (1.25 mg/0.05 mL) were administered through the pars plana using a 30-gauge needle under aseptic conditions, preceded by local anesthesia and topical povidone-iodine. Patients received topical antibiotics four times daily for one week. Final intraocular pressure was measured one-month post-injection to evaluate treatment outcomes.

Results: In this study of 60 non-glaucomatous patients with macular edema, 22 (36.7%) were male and 38 (63.3%) female, with a mean age of 42.25 ± 7.57 years, mean weight 77.33 ± 16.75 kg, height 157.87 ± 10.38 cm, and BMI 31.43 ± 7.98 kg/m². Most patients lived in urban areas (55.0%), while 45.0% resided rurally. Diabetes was the most common comorbidity (36.7%), followed by

hypertension (28.3%) and age-related macular degeneration (23.3%), with 11.7% having none. Educationally, 58.3% had intermediate to graduate-level qualifications, and 63.3% belonged to the middle socioeconomic class. Eye involvement was bilateral in 45.0% of patients, right-sided in 30.0%, and left-sided in 25.0%. The mean procedure time for intravitreal Avastin injection was 6.43 ± 1.47 minutes. Mean intraocular pressure (IOP) rose from 13.87 ± 1.35 mmHg preoperatively to 18.53 ± 1.07 mmHg at one week, then declined to 15.67 ± 1.04 mmHg after one month, showing a significant increase (mean difference = -1.80 ± 0.55 mmHg; $p < 0.001$). Stratified analyses by gender and residence revealed similar patterns, and ANOVA confirmed no significant effect of gender ($p = 0.330$) or residence ($p = 0.780$) on IOP trends, indicating consistent postoperative changes across all groups.

Conclusion: This study confirms that intravitreal Avastin significantly mild increases IOP in non-glaucomatous macular edema patients, with consistent effects across gender, residence, and common comorbidities. These results emphasize Avastin's role in effectively treating macular edema while mild increase in IOP.

INTRODUCTION

Macular edema (ME) is a common cause of blindness, primarily affecting patients with associated systemic diseases, including diabetic and retinal vascular diseases. ME is a multifactorial disease with a complex pathophysiology characterized by extracellular fluid accumulation in the macula, resulting from the disruption of the blood-retinal barrier (1). This buildup results in the thickening of the retina, central vision distortion, and a loss of visual acuity. In DME, IC3B, sub capillary hemorrhage, cotton wool spots, and microaneurysms can result from chronic hyperglycemia that leads to microvascular injury, increased permeability, and leakage. With the increasing prevalence of diabetes mellitus in the world, ME is likely to increase as well in the future (2). ME, particularly DME, is very common in Pakistan, and its prevalence is high and on the rise. The country is rapidly reaching epidemic proportions of diabetes mellitus (DM), and according to recent estimates, over 33 million individuals have DM at present (3). Rising numbers have a direct bearing on ocular health, since diabetes is strongly associated with the development of diabetic retinal complications, such as ME. Metropolitan cities like Karachi, Lahore, and Rawalpindi have reported a higher prevalence of diabetic eye diseases and have been in consistent increase (urbanization, population

aggregation, and more easily available diagnostic facilities being the cause). For example, one study from Rawalpindi showed that DME was a major cause of ME burden overall, which calls for effective screening and management of this condition on an urgent basis (4).

The therapeutic picture of ME has developed significantly in the past two decades. One of the most important developments is the use of intravitreal anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti- VEGF) agents. Bevacizumab (Avastin), a recombinant monoclonal antibody targeting VEGFA, has become a cornerstone in the therapy of ME (5). Bevacizumab was not initially formulated for oncological treatment, but has rather gained widespread off-label use in retinal disorders such as DME and ME secondary to retinal vein occlusion. Its MOA is by VEGF-induced vascular permeability blockade, resulting in decreased fluid accumulation to facilitate the absorption of macular edema (6). Efficacy of intravitreal bevacizumab has been established in various clinical trials and "real-life" studies, showing significant improvement in both anatomical and functional outcomes. A marked decrease in central retinal thickness as measured by optical coherence tomography (OCT) is reported, usually with a parallel improvement in visual acuity. In the health care setting of Pakistan,

bevacizumab is especially useful because of its comparatively low cost as compared with other anti-VEGF agents such as ranibizumab or aflibercept, which makes it affordable for a larger percentage of the public (7). Its clinical advantages have also been verified in a few studies conducted in Pakistan, where response has been shown not only in the retinal morphology but also in the vision post-treatment. Although intravitreal bevacizumab has been used frequently with efficacy, the safety of the method is continually considered. One of the concerns is that the IOP increases after the injection. IOP is an important factor of ocular physiology, and chronic increases in IOP may result in glaucomatous optic neuropathy and irreversible visual loss

(8). IOP may acutely elevate due to increased intraocular volume during the immediate post-injection period, although it will generally return to baseline within minutes to hours. However, there is controversy about the long-term effect of repeated injections of anti-VEGF agents on IOP, especially in patients with glaucoma or ocular hypertension (9). There are few reports on changes in IOP after intravitreal bevacizumab injections in Pakistan, and it appears that no studies so far have investigated such changes in this population, particularly non-glaucomatous. An institutional study from the District Headquarter Teaching Hospital, Gujranwala, included diabetic patients using bevacizumab for DME. The results indicated a statistically significant short-term increase in IOP following injection, but no sustained increase in IOP after follow-up at one month (10). This implies that, although an acute elevation in the IOP is a widespread symptom phenomenon, it might not involve long-term risk to glaucoma naïve patients. However, these findings are obtained from a small sample size and a short follow-up, which suggests a necessity of larger and longer follow-up studies. With increased utilization of intravitreal bevacizumab in ophthalmology services throughout Pakistan and the possibilities for an iatrogenic risk of IOP, more work is warranted

(11). Of greater interest will be to define the average change in IOP with treatment, and to document whether repeated injections add to a cumulative

rise in IOP as time progresses. This information is crucial to establish safe and effective clinical guidelines for bevacizumab therapy (12). This study aims to bridge this gap and determine the mean IOP change after intravitreal bevacizumab injections in non-glaucomatous ME patients at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi. Knowledge gained from the results of this study is anticipated to bring important information on short and medium-term ocular effects of bevacizumab and improve rational decisions for the treatment of ME in clinical practice. Through better knowledge of the IOP response locally, ophthalmologists could better decide on patient surveillance, intervals of follow-up, and adjunctive therapy for high-risk patients.

Methodology

This quasi-experimental study (non-randomized control trial) was conducted at the Department of Ophthalmology, Liaquat National Hospital, Karachi, from November 11th 2024 to April 12th 2025, using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. The sample included individuals aged 30 to 55 years of any gender diagnosed with non-glaucomatous macular edema. Patients treated with platelet-rich plasma (PRP), those with a history of ocular trauma, or those using beta blockers or steroid-containing eye drops were excluded to minimize confounding and bias. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant. Eligible patients underwent a thorough ophthalmic and systemic evaluation, including unaided and best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA), slit lamp and fundus examination, intraocular pressure (IOP) measurement. Visual acuity was assessed using Snellen charts, and IOP was measured with a contact tonometer. Anterior segment biomicroscopy and indirect ophthalmoscopy were performed, and anterior segment photographs were taken. Intravitreal injections of bevacizumab (1.25 mg/0.05 mL) were administered through the pars plana using a 30-gauge needle under aseptic conditions. Eyes were pre-treated with 5% povidone-iodine and topical antibiotics, and post-injection care included antibiotic drops four times daily for one week. Sterile cotton was used post-injection to prevent

reflux. IOP was reassessed one month post-injection. Bias was minimized by strictly adhering to the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

RESULTS

Out of a total of 60 non-glaucomatous patients diagnosed with macular edema, 22 (36.7%) were male and 38 (63.3%) were female. The mean age of the 60 patients was 42.25 ± 7.57 years, with a mean weight of 77.33 ± 16.75 kg, a mean height of 157.87 ± 10.38 cm, and a mean BMI of 31.43 ± 7.98 kg/m². Regarding place of residence, 60 patients were studied, with 33 (55.0%) residing in urban areas and 27 (45.0%) in rural areas (Table 1).

Concerning comorbidities, diabetes was the most common, present in 22 patients (36.7%), followed by hypertension in 17 patients (28.3%), and age-related macular degeneration in 14 patients (23.3%). Only 7 patients (11.7%) reported no

comorbid conditions. Regarding educational status, the majority of patients had attained intermediate (17 patients, 28.3%) or graduate-level education (18 patients, 30.0%), while fewer had primary (8.3%), secondary (11.7%), or matriculation (21.7%) education. In terms of socioeconomic status, most patients belonged to the middle class (38 patients, 63.3%), with equal smaller proportions from the upper (11 patients, 18.3%) and lower classes (11 patients, 18.3%) (Table 1).

Regarding eye involvement, 18 patients (30.0%) had right eye involvement, 15 (25.0%) had left eye involvement, and 27 (45.0%) had bilateral involvement, showing that nearly half of the cases affected both eyes. The procedure time for intravitreal Avastin (bevacizumab) injection in non- glaucomatous eyes had a mean duration of 6.43 ± 1.47 minutes (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of non-glaucomatous patients with macular edema (n = 60)

Socio-Demographics	N (%) / Mean \pm SD
Total=135	
Gender	
Male	22 (36.7%)
Female	38 (63.3%)
Anthropometric measurements	
Age (in years)	42.25 ± 7.57
Weight (in kg)	77.33 ± 16.75
Height (in cm)	157.87 ± 10.38
BMI (kg/m ²)	31.43 ± 7.98
Residential status	
Urban	33 (55%)
Rural	27 (45%)
Comorbidities	
Diabetes Mellitus	22 (36.7%)
Hypertension	17 (28.3%)
Age-related macular degeneration	14 (23.3%)
None	7 (11.7%)
Education Status	
Primary	5 (8.3%)
Secondary	7 (11.7%)
Matriculation	13 (21.7%)
Intermediate	17 (28.3%)
Graduate	18 (30%)

Socioeconomic Status	
Upper	11 (18.3%)
Middle	38 (63.3%)
Lower	11 (18.3%)
Eye Involvement	
Right Eye	18 (30%)
Left Eye	15 (25%)
Bilateral	27 (45%)
Mean Procedure Time (minutes)	6.43 ± 1.47

The mean intraocular pressure (IOP) showed a progressive rise following the injection. Preoperatively, the mean IOP was 13.87 ± 1.35 mmHg, which increased transiently to 18.53 ± 1.07 mmHg at one week postoperatively, indicating an

initial postoperative elevation. However, this rise was followed by a steady decrease over time, with the mean IOP reducing to 16.67 ± 1.04 mmHg at two weeks and further to 15.67 ± 1.04 mmHg at one month (Table 2).

Table 2. Mean intraocular pressure (IOP) at different time intervals.

Time Interval	N	Mean ± SD (mmHg)
Preoperative	60	13.87 ± 1.35
Postoperative at 1 week	60	18.87 ± 1.35
Postoperative at 2 weeks	60	16.67 ± 1.04
Postoperative after 1 month	60	15.67 ± 1.04

In this study, intraocular pressure (IOP) was measured preoperatively and at one month postoperatively in 60 patients. The mean preoperative IOP was 13.87 ± 1.35 mmHg, which increased to 15.67 ± 1.04 mmHg one month after surgery. A paired-samples t-test revealed a significant mean difference of -1.80 ± 0.55 mmHg ($t = -25.53$, $p < 0.001$), with a 95% confidence interval of -1.94 to -1.66 mmHg. These findings indicate a statistically significant rise in IOP one month postoperatively, demonstrating a consistent increase across the patient cohort (Table 3).

Moreover, in our study, intraocular pressure (IOP) was also measured preoperatively and at one month postoperatively in 60 patients, stratified by both gender and place of residence. Among males, the mean preoperative IOP was 13.73 ± 1.45 mmHg, increasing to 15.45 ± 1.10 mmHg at

one month postoperatively, with a significant mean difference of -1.73 ± 0.55 mmHg ($t = -14.72$, $p < 0.001$; 95% CI: -1.97 to -1.48). Among females, the mean preoperative IOP was 13.95 ± 1.29 mmHg, rising to 15.79 ± 0.99 mmHg postoperatively, with a mean difference of -1.84 ± 0.55 mmHg ($t = -20.78$, $p < 0.001$; 95% CI: -2.02 to -1.66). When stratified by place of residence, urban patients ($n = 33$) had a preoperative mean IOP of 13.91 ± 1.31 mmHg, which increased to 15.70 ± 1.05 mmHg postoperatively, yielding a significant mean difference of -1.79 ± 0.48 mmHg ($t = -21.19$, $p < 0.001$; 95% CI: -1.96 to -1.62). Rural patients ($n = 27$) showed a preoperative mean IOP of 13.81 ± 1.42 mmHg, rising to 15.63 ± 1.04 mmHg at one month, with a mean difference of -1.81 ± 0.62 mmHg ($t = -15.15$, $p < 0.001$; 95% CI: -2.06 to -1.57) (Table 3).

Table 3: Comparison of preoperative and 1-month postoperative mean intraocular pressure (IOP) in non-glaucomatous patients with macular edema overall and by gender and place of residence

Groups	Preoperative Mean IOP (mmHg) at baseline	Postoperative Mean IOP (mmHg) after 1- month	Mean Difference (mmHg)	t-value	p-value
Overall (n=60)	13.87 ± 1.35	15.67 ± 1.04	-1.80	-25.53	<0.001*
Gender					
Male (n=22)	13.73 ± 1.45	15.45 ± 1.10	-1.73	14.72	<0.001*
Female (n=38)	13.95 ± 1.29	15.79 ± 0.99	-1.84	20.78	<0.001*
Place of Residence					
Urban (n=33)	13.91 ± 1.31	15.70 ± 1.05	-1.79	21.19	<0.001*
Rural (n=27)	13.81 ± 1.42	15.63 ± 1.04	-1.81	15.15	<0.001*

Between-subject’s analyses of variance (ANOVA) were conducted to examine the effects of gender and place of residence on average intraocular pressure (IOP) across all time points. The analysis revealed that gender had no statistically significant effect on IOP ($F = 0.966, p = 0.330$), indicating that the overall pattern of IOP change over time was similar in males and females. Similarly, place of residence (urban vs. rural) was not a significant factor ($F = 0.079, p = 0.780$), suggesting

comparable trends in IOP change across residential groups. In both analyses, the intercepts were highly significant (gender: $F = 12,025.383, p < 0.001$; residence: $F = 12,677.74, p < 0.001$), reflecting the overall variation in IOP measurements. These results indicate that while IOP increased initially postoperatively and then gradually decreased over one month, this trajectory was consistent regardless of gender or place of residence (Table 4).

Table 4. Mean intraocular pressure (IOP) across time points by gender and place of residence with ANOVA analysis.

Variables	Preoperative IOP (mmHg)	1 Week Post-op (mmHg)	2 Weeks Post-op (mmHg)	1 Month Post-op (mmHg)	ANOVA p-value
Gender					
Male (n=22)	13.73 ± 1.45	18.36 ± 1.14	16.45 ± 1.10	15.45 ± 1.10	0.330
Female (n=38)	13.95 ± 1.29	18.63 ± 1.02	16.79 ± 0.99	15.79 ± 0.99	
Place of residence					
Urban (n=33)	13.91 ± 1.31	18.58 ± 1.03	16.70 ± 1.05	15.70 ± 1.05	0.780
Rural (n=27)	13.81 ± 1.42	18.48 ± 1.12	16.63 ± 1.04	15.63 ± 1.04	

Discussion:

The present study aimed to assess the intraocular pressure of non-glaucomatous patients with macular edema in a tertiary care hospital, Karachi, due to intravitreal injection of Avastin (bevacizumab). Results show a significant rise in IOP after injection. The mean pre-operative IOP was 13.87 ± 1.35 mmHg, which rose to 15.67 ± 1.04 mmHg at one-month post-operative with a mean difference of -1.80 ± 0.55 mmHg, $p < 0.001$. According to the pattern of IOP elevation, there is initially a rise in IOP (mean IOP 18.53 ± 1.07 mmHg) occurring in the first week after injection. This rise reverts to a normal level in consecutive weeks. However, it will depend on the actual concentrations and volumes applied, as well as the route of drug uptake. The findings were consistent with the pharmacodynamic effect known of anti-VEGF therapy. The IOP may increase temporarily owing to the immediate volume effect of injections of the intravitreal site. In addition, transient obstruction of the trabecular meshwork may also occur.

When split by gender, males and females had similar IOP trends. However, females had a mean rise of 1.84 ± 0.55 mmHg, and males had a mean rise of 1.73 ± 0.55 mmHg. This was not statistically significant (ANOVA, $p = 0.330$). Likewise, the trends among urban and rural patients were comparable (1.79 ± 0.48 mmHg (urban) vs. 1.81 ± 0.62 mmHg (rural); ANOVA, $p = 0.780$), indicating that gender and place of residence did not influence postoperative IOP. The consistency of this pattern among subgroups indicates that the IOP rise is likely due to the procedure, and not to the patients.

Our findings are consistent with previously published literature. Mansoori et al. recorded that intravitreal injection of bevacizumab raised IOP measurably within days of injection, which wouldn't return to baseline values until about a month after, and IOP would spike once more (13). Avery et al. (2014) confirmed the safety of bevacizumab with the demonstration of low-level but short-term IOP spikes in patients without glaucoma, and this stresses the need for early postoperative monitoring (5). Our study does not merely have an eye on IOP changes right after

injection, like some studies do. A detailed assessment at four intervals, which are preoperative, 1 week, 2 weeks, and 1 month, gives a better picture of the IOP and shows that the early spike subsides over time and does not persist at harmful levels.

The cohort studied clinically consisted mostly of middle-aged patients (mean age 42.25 ± 7.57 years), along with a higher amount of female patients (63.3%) having comorbidities like diabetes mellitus (36.7%) and hypertension (28.3%). Almost every other patient had macular edema in both eyes, which shows how the eyes get affected as the disease keeps getting worse. The baseline characteristics are important because systemic co-morbidities may alter ocular perfusion and retinal vascular integrity, such that IOP variations may be influenced (14). Even with these factors, our results show that the size and direction of pressure in the eye after injection remained similar for all patient groups (15).

The comparison of equivalent reductions in IOP between urban and rural patients, suggesting that environmental or lifestyle influences related to domicile do not significantly impact IOP lowering from Avastin. Lee et al. (2020) also found a weak influence of socioeconomic and environmental factors on IOP increase following the repeated intravitreal injections (16). This adds support to the idea that the physiological events attributed to be caused by Avastin override the contributions of extrinsic factors toward IOP outcomes (17).

Comorbid conditions, including diabetes (36.7%) and hypertension (28.3%), were common in our cohort, which is consistent with standard macular edema populations. The study did not demonstrate a reduction in strength. Despite these systemic vascular conditions which can complicate ocular hemodynamics and elevate glaucoma risk the study showed consistent IOP reduction post-Avastin. Daka et al. (2023) in their meta-analysis confirmed the overall safety of anti-VEGF agents even in patients with systemic vascular diseases, with no signs of adverse IOP spikes or development of glaucoma (18). Such reassurance is clinically relevant as other comorbidities, such as systemic hypertension and glaucoma, are often found in macular edema patients.

The average time for the intravitreal injection procedure was short (6.43 ± 1.47 minutes). Thus, there was little scope for variability in the procedure. It further supports the idea that the increase in IOP was a physiological response to the drug and did not have technical aspects. Notably, all IOP readings during the follow-up visit at all 3 time points were found to be within a clinically acceptable range and thus, transient elevations are clinically unlikely to pose immediate ocular risk in a non-glaucomatous eye. The research suggests that for most patients, routine short-term monitoring of IOP post-injection is adequate. However, high-risk patients, such as those with predisposing ocular hypertension or glaucoma, should be monitored more closely.

Conclusion: - The study shows that intravitreal Avastin causes a mild but significant increase in the eye's pressure, which is considered normal in patients who do not have glaucoma or ocular hypertension. The findings did not differ among gender and residential subgroups, which is also consistent with previously published evidence, supporting the safety profile of Avastin and the need for postoperative follow-up. This result will help the clinicians of tertiary care facilities with the efficacy and safety of anti-VEGF therapy for macular edema management.

Conflict of interest: - The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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